

(CASE REPORT)

Management of *Manasa Bhava* and Lifestyle Modification in *Prameha* with special reference to Diabetes Mellitus: A case study

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Abstract

Diabetes Mellitus is one of the most common endocrine disorder. Diabetes is a Greek word meaning 'a passer through: a siphon' and mellitus derives from the Greek word for 'Sweet'. Diabetes Mellitus is burning problem of 21st century. The Greeks named it thus due to the excessive amounts of urine produced by sufferers which attracted insects because of its glucose content¹. Ayurveda explains this concept about thousands years ago in the context of Prameha. As we know that there are various factors responsible for development of Prameha like Aaharaja Hetu, Viharaja Hetu, improper Dinacharya and now a day's Manasika Hetus are also versening the disease formation. So treatment of Manasa Bhavas are also important in the Prameha. Majority of the Diabetic patient is mentally upset. Psychology of the person determines effect of the Diabetes or severity of the Diabetes. Shirodhara & Shamana Chikitsa is useful to control Manasa Bhava & Prameha.

Keywords: Case report; Manasa Bhava; Lifestyle; Prameha; Diabetes Mellitus

1. Introduction

India is becoming a new age hub for the life style disorders. As the impact of globalization, Indians are having vast exposure to western lifestyle especially food culture. Indians are leaving back their traditional food culture replacing it with convenient western food culture. As a result we are coping with new age food which might not be genetically compatible to Indians, growing urbanization and sedentary lifestyle further more adding risk of being susceptible to acquire pre-diabetic conditions which may worsen into established picture of diabetes mellitus. *Ayurveda* is an ancient medical science which is based on scientific principles, described diabetes under the name of *Prameha* or *Madhumeha*.

According to WHO, Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder of multiple etiology which is characterized by chronic hyperglycemia with disturbance of carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism resulting from defects of insulin secretion, insulin action or both^[2]. Diabetes is one of the leading causes of death in the world and India is set to emerge as the diabetic capital of the world. An estimated 29.1 million people (9.3%) in the United States have Diabetes Mellitus, of which approximately 1.25 million have type 1 Diabetes and most of the rest have type 2 Diabetes. A third group designated as "Other specific types" by the American Diabetes Association (ADA) number only in the thousands². Diabetes Mellitus is burning problem of 21st century. Every 20 second one Diabetic patient in World is losing his lower limb. Every 6 seconds a person dies from Diabetes. (In 5th IDF Conf. 2013, Melbourne). Diabetes leads to death of 10 lakh Indians every year^[3].

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One of the important causing factor in *Prameha* is *Manasika hetu*. This *hetus* are now progress very fast and found in all disease. Stress is very important causing agent, due to any reason. *Acharyas* explained that due to excessive *Kama*, *Krodha*, *Shoka*, *Bhaya* and *Chinta* there is development of *Apatarpanjanya Prameha*. Therefore mental health management is more important and it helps in improving immunity, stronger the body & mind & decreases complications.

2. Case report

A 35 year old male having following complaints since from 2-3 months. Patients *Nidana* was done initially along with *Ashtavidha & Dashavidha Pariksha*.

2.1. Chief complaints

- Hasta Pada tala Daha
- Anidra
- Naktamutrata

2.2. General Examination

PR = 80/min

CVS = No murmurs, S1, S2 Normal

BP = 130/90 mm of Hg

CNS = Conscious, Oriented

RS = AE=BE, Clear, 22/min

P/A = Soft, No tenderness

2.3. Ashtavidha Pariksha

- Nadi - 80/min
- Mala - Samyaka
- Mutra - Naktamutrata
- Jivha - Alpa Sama
- Shabda - Spashta
- Sparsha - Anushna
- Druka - Prakruta
- 8. Akruiti - Madhyama

2.4. Personal History

No exercise, Working in sitting position, No walking, *Ratrau-Jagarana*, *Divaswapa*, No proper following *Dinacharya*.

2.5. Family History

No History of Paternal / Maternal Diabetes Mellitus.

2.6. Past History

No History of any major disease illness.

Patient is under the stress of his work and worrying about *Prameha*, leads to *Ati-Chinta*, *Anidra*,

Krodha, *Shoka* etc.

2.7. Etiology

2.7.1. Aaharaja Hetu

Guru Aahara like Fast food, Samosas, Maida flour *Dravyas*, *Pruthaka*, *Dadhi sevana*, excessive consumption of Coffee, *Madhura rasa*, etc.

2.7.2. Viharaja Hetu

Divaswapa, Swapnasukham (Sitting work + eating food), *Avyayama, Ratrau-Jagarana*, etc.

2.7.3. Manasa Hetu

Ati-Chinta, Stress, Krodha, Shoka, etc

2.8. Pathology[4]

Figure 1 Pathophysiology of Prameha

According to *Charaka*, due to prolonged causes like *Aasy sukha* (sedentary life style), *SwapnaSukha* (excessive sleep), in dietary habits, *Dadhini* (increased intake of curd), *Gramya-audak-anup-rasa* (increased intake flesh of pet, aquatic, and animals where moisture is more), *payamsi* (milk and its products), *Navaannapan* (more consumption of new grains), *Gudvaikrutam* (increased consumption of jaggery products) there is an accumulation of *Bahudrava Shleshma* i.e. excess *Kapha Dosh*a with increased fluidity. It further leads to increase in *Kleda*. As *Kleda* which is essential for *Dhatu Samhanan*

is increased, it causes vitiation of *Dushyas* which are *Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Meda, Asthi, Majja, Shukra, Ambu, Vasa, Lasika, Aja*. Accumulation of *Kapha* in *Dushyas* leads to *Dhatu shaithilya*, especially in *meda* and *mamsa*.

This vitiated *Kapha Dosha* further causes vitiation of *Kleda* (fluid portion of the body) thereby converting it into *Mutra*. These vitiated *Dosha, Kleda* and *Ddhatus* get accumulated at *Basti region* and Also increased *Kapha Dosha* further accumulates itself at orifices of *mutravaha strotas* which are originated from *basti*, where *gaurava* is already seen due to the accumulation of vitiated *Meda* and *Kleda*. This brings chronic as well as incurable nature to *vyadhi Prameha*.⁽⁴⁸⁾ According to this combination of *Doshas* with different *Dushyas, Prameha* is classified into twenty types, according to properties of urine.

2.9. Management

2.9.1. Kwatha^[5]

Darvi, Devadaru, Triphala, Musta Churna, Matra - 2 Pala, Kala - Adhobhakta.

2.9.2. Vasanta Kusumakara Rasa^[6]

Matra - 250 mgm, Klala - Adhobhakta, Anupana - Ushnodaka.

2.9.3. Shirodhara^[7]

Jatamansi siddha taila for 15 days.

2.9.4. Brahmi Ghrita^[8]

At morning time, empty stomach, 10 gm with *Ushnodaka*.

2.9.5. 5. Dinacharya Palana^[10]

It is very important to follow because waking up at the time of *Brahma Muhurta* leads to secretion of Cortisol.

Observations

Effect of the treatment on Hasta Pada-tala daha, Anidra , Naktamutrata, etc.

Table 1 Effect of treatment on symptoms

	Symptoms	Before treatment	After treatment
VAS Scale	<i>Hasta Padatala daha</i>	10	5
VAS Scale	Naktamutrata	+++	++

2.10. Gradation of Symptoms

1 - 3 = Mild ; 4 - 6 = Moderate ; 7 - 10 = Severe

+ = Mild , ++ = Moderate , +++ = Severe

3. Result

Table 2 Effect of treatment on blood sugar level

BSL	Fasting	Postprandial
Before treatment	220 mg/dl	398 mg/dl
After treatment	198 mg/dl	218 mg/dl

4. Discussion

In this study, observations are done before and after treatment based on BSL values and also with the help of *Manasa Bhava parikshana* i.e. *Satva parikshana* & *Satva sara parikshana*.

4.1. Darvyadi Kwatha

It contains *Darvi*, *Devadaru*, *Triphala* & *Musta* which helps to reduce blood sugar. Berberine presents in *Darvi* helps to reduce the Blood sugar level in the body. *Devadaru* is rich with antidiabetic active constituents like Flavonoids, Tannins & Embelin. *Triphala*, *Musta* have a direct action of Anti-diabetic. *Aamalaki*, *Darvi*, *Triphala*, *Musta* having actions like *Raktaprasadana*, *Kushthahara*. Therefore it helpful in Skin lesions produced in *Prameha*.

4.2. Vasanta Kusumakara Rasa

It contains *Suvarna*, *Roupya*, *Vanga bhasma* & etc *dravyas* which helps to reduce *Prameha roga*. It is important *Kalpa* used in *Prameha*. It helps to prevents from the development of Diabetic retinopathy, Polyurea.

4.3. Shirodhara of Jatamansi siddha taila

As patient is suffering from lots of stress, *Chinta* etc. therefore *shirodhara* is given which is helps to reduce stress & provides *Samyaka nidra*.

4.4. Brahmi Ghrita

Its *snehapana* is very helpful to reduce stress & *Manasa bhava*.

5. Conclusion

In this case all symptoms like *Hasta pada tala daha*, *Anidra*, *Naktamutrata* markedly diminished in the 2 months study. The given treatment the drugs acts on the *dosha-dushya* of *Prameha* which helps to reduce the blood sugar level in the body. In conclusion, *Darvyadi Kwatha* etc. treatment are significantly effective in the management of *Prameha* followed by proper *Pathya -Aapathya* and proper *Satva Parikshana*.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there was no conflict of interest regarding the publication of manuscript.

Statement of informed consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the individual participant included in the study.

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Author's short biography

Dr. Sachinkumar Sahebrao Patil. I am working as a Ayurved Physician, Panchakarma Specialist since 17 Years. I am a BOARD OF STUDIES MEMBER for Paraclinical Ayurved Board of Maharashtra University of Health Sciences Nashik. I am a FACULTY MEMBER for Post Graduate Paraclinical Ayurved Board of Maharashtra University of Health Sciences, Nashik. I am working as a Research Faculty for Research Methodogy and Medical Statistics of Maharashtra University of Health Sciences, Nashik. I am a Ph.D. GUIDE for five Ph.D. Kayachikitsa (Medicine) students and M.D. GUIDE for 26 M.D. Kayachikitsa (Medicine) students out of which 18 M.D. Kayachikitsa (Medicine) students. My research experience is 14 Years. My research interest in Anxiety Disorder, Diabetes Mellitus, Obesity, Hyperacidity, Diarrhoea, Anaemia etc.